

ComTraForce

**REPORT OF REVIEW OF
FORCE CALIBRATION
FACILITIES**

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Prepared by

Andy KNOTT (NPL)

Haldun DIZDAR (TUBITAK UME)

Bulent AYDEMIR (TUBITAK UME)

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Further information

For further information about this document and project, you can find web page.

(see <https://www.ptb.de/empir2019/comtraforce/home/>).

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<p>See diagram to right - please give details of any calibration/measurement services performed with continuous or dynamic (sinusoidal, shock, or step) forces:</p>	<p>In our laboratory, static calibration of force transducers is performed according to ISO 376 and ASTM E74 standards, on the other hand quasi-static (continuous) calibration of force measuring devices is performed according to DKD R 3-9 Guideline. Furthermore, static calibration of material testing machine is performed concernig to ISO 7500-1 and ASTM E4 standards. Our laboratory does not provide dynamic calibration service.</p>	
<p>Please include details of measurement principle, force range and rate/frequency, calibration method, and industrial sector:</p>	<p>In our laboratory, static calibration of force transducers is provided between 0,5 N -3000 kN force range. On the other hand quasi-static (continuous) calibration of force measuring devices is provided between 0-100 kN force range according to comparison method of reference and test force sensors. Furthermore, static calibration of material testing machine is provided up to 0-1 MN for tension and compression force application mode also 3 MN-10 MN force range for compression force application mode.</p>	
<p>If not, please give details of any ongoing research towards providing, or industrial demands for, such services:</p>		

<p>Number of accredited force calibration laboratories in your country:</p>	<p>There are three laboratories accredited for calibration of force-proving instruments</p>	
<p>Number of accredited force testing laboratories in your country:</p>	<p>There are thirty six laboratories accredited for calibration of testing machines, on the other hand there are two laboratories accredited for verification of constant amplitude dynamic forces in an axial fatigue testing system</p>	
<p>Most common materials tests, e.g. tensile / fatigue / hardness / impact / other:</p>	<p>Tension, compression, hardness, fatigue</p>	

Country	NMI / Labs	Calibration/ Test Type	Machine Name	Machine Type	Measurement Range	Measurement Uncertainty	Manufacturer	Method	Details	Number of Laboratory
TURKEY	TUBITAK UME	Static	Force Standard Machines (FSM)	Dead Weight FSM	20 N - 600 N	2×10^{-5}	TUBITAK UME	ISO 376		
				Dead Weight FSM	20 N - 1 kN	2×10^{-5}	TUBITAK UME	ISO 376		
				Dead Weight FSM	100 N - 11 kN	2×10^{-5}	GTM	ISO 376		
				Dead Weight FSM	2 kN - 110 kN	2×10^{-5}	GTM	ISO 376		
				Lever Amplification FSM	20 kN - 1100 kN	1×10^{-4}	GTM	ISO 376		
				Comparator with three reference force transducers	50 kN - 3 MN	5×10^{-4}	OZMAK	ISO 376		
		Material Testing Machine	Tension and Compression	20 kN - 250 kN	0,16%	Zwick	ISO 7500-1			
			Tension and Compression	1 kN - 10 kN	0,16%	Zwick	ISO 7500-1			
			Tension and Compression	50 N - 500 N	0,16%	Zwick	ISO 7500-1			
			Compression	150 kN - 3000 kN	0,32%	Utest	ISO 7500-1			
		Continuous (Quasi-Static)	Piezo sensor + Material Testing Machine + Force Standard Machines + Data Acquisition System	Tension and Compression	(0,5 kN - 300 kN/ Compression) (0,5 kN - 120 kN/ Tension-Compression)	0,10%	Kistler+Zwick+GTM	DKD-R 3-9		
		Dynamic	Piezo sensor + Material Testing Machine + Data Acquisition System	Compression		> 2%	Kistler+MTS			

TURKEY	OTHER FORCE MEASUREMENT INFRASTRUCTURE	Dynamic	Piezo sensor + Material Testing Machine + Data Acquisition System	Compression		> 2%	Kistler+MTS				
		Static	Force Calibration Machines (FCM)	Tension and Compression	1 N - 245,16 kN	0,01 % - 0,03%	ESIT, UVE	ISO 376, ASTM E74	In the tension and compression force application direction with dead-weighted force calibration machine	There are three laboratories accredited for calibration of force-proving instruments	
			Reference Force-proving Instruments	Tension and Compression	0,1 mN - 3000 kN	0,10 % - 0,32%	-	ISO 7500-1, ASTM E4	Calibration is performed with force capacities of 2000 N and above, by using Class 0.5 and Class 1 force-proving instruments according to ISO 376 standard, in the direction of compression and tension by using dead weights in force capacities below 2000 N.	There are thirty six laboratories accredited for calibration of testing machines	
		Continuous (Quasi-Static)	Not Available								
		Dynamic	Reference Force-proving Instruments	Tension	5 kN - 50 kN	0,24%	-	MIL STD 1312B, ASTM E467, ISO 4965-2	-	There are two laboratories accredited for verification of constant amplitude dynamic forces in an axial fatigue testing system	

General view of TUBITAK UME 110 kN Deadweight and 1100 kN Lever Amplification Force Standard Machines

General view of TUBITAK UME 3000 kN Hydraulic Build Up Force Standard Machine

General view of TUBITAK UME 1 kN Deadweight Force Standard Machines

General view of TUBITAK UME 11 kN Force Standard Machine

NMI:

TUBITAK UME (TURKAK accredited)

Deadweight machines:

0,1 N to 200 N, $U(k=2) = 0.002\%$

0.1 kN to 1,1 kN, $U(k=2) = 0.002\%$

0,1 kN to 11 kN, $U(k=2) = 0.002\%$

2 kN to 110 kN, $U(k=2) = 0.002\%$

Lever machine:

20 kN to 1,1 MN (lever amplification), $U(k=2) = 0.01\%$

Hydraulic machine:

50 kN to 3 MN (built-up machine), $U(k=2) = 0.04\%$

Other TURKAK accredited labs for ISO 376 / ASTM E74 calibrations:

TSE

Deadweight machines:

1 N to 200 N, $U(k=2) = 0.005\%$

0.1 kN to 1,1 kN, $U(k=2) = 0.005\%$

0,1 kN to 11 kN, $U(k=2) = 0.005\%$

2 kN to 110 kN, $U(k=2) = 0.005\%$

KALMET

Deadweight machines:

1 N to 200 N, $U(k=2) = 0.01\%$

0.1 kN to 1,1 kN, $U(k=2) = 0.01\%$

0,1 kN to 20 kN, $U(k=2) = 0.01\%$

Hydraulic machine:

20 kN to 2 MN, $U(k=2) = 0.03\%$

10 kN to 500 kN, $U(k=2) = 0.05\%$

ESIT

Deadweight machines:

0,5 kg to 60 kg, $U(k=2) = 0.02\%$

10 kg to 500 kg, $U(k=2) = 0.01\%$

40 kg to 2000 kg, $U(k=2) = 0.01\%$

1000 kg to 25000 kg, $U(k=2) = 0.028\%$

THY

Hydraulic machine:

$0,45\text{ kN} \leq F \leq 4,5\text{ kN}$, $U(k=2) = 0.12\%$

$2\text{ kN} \leq F \leq 40\text{ kN}$, $U(k=2) = 0.12\%$

$40\text{ kN} \leq F \leq 100\text{ kN}$, $U(k=2) = 0.05\%$

$40\text{ kN} \leq F \leq 200\text{ kN}$, $U(k=2) = 0.3\%$

Numbers of TURKAK accredited laboratories for calibration of testing machines:

Compression testing machines: 51

Creep testing machines: 1

Impact testing machines: 9

Tensile testing machines: 51

Alignment measurement: 1

NPL / UNITED KINGDOM

Name:	Andy Knott																			
email address:	andy.knott@npl.co.uk																			
NMI / Country:	NPL/UNITED KINGDOM																			
Services performed by NMI:	Calibration of force transducers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																		
	Calibration of testing machines	<input type="checkbox"/>																		
	Mechanical tests	<input type="checkbox"/>																		
	Other:	<input type="checkbox"/>																		
Force machines at NMI:			< 10 N	25 N - 2,5 kN	0,5 kN - 20 kN	2,5 kN - 120 kN	10 kN - 1,2 MN	> 1 MN												
	Deadweight	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>												
	Amplification	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																	
	Comparison	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																	
	Other:	<input type="checkbox"/>																		
NMI has CMCs in BIPM KCDB:	YES	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																		
	NO, but intend to submit in next 3 years	<input type="checkbox"/>																		
	NO	<input type="checkbox"/>																		
Documentary standards used for calibration of force transducers and testing machines:	ISO 376:2011; ASTM E74-18																			

<p>See diagram to right - please give details of any calibration/measurement services performed with continuous or dynamic (sinusoidal, shock, or step) forces:</p>		
<p>Please include details of measurement principle, force range and rate/frequency, calibration method, and industrial sector:</p>		
<p>If not, please give details of any ongoing research towards providing, or industrial demands for, such services:</p>		
<p>Number of accredited force calibration laboratories in your country:</p>	<p>10 laboratories</p>	
<p>Number of accredited force testing laboratories in your country:</p>	<p>13 laboratories</p>	
<p>Most common materials tests, e.g. tensile / fatigue / hardness / impact / other:</p>	<p>Most common material tests: Tensile, compression, impact, creep, concrete</p>	

NMI:

Deadweight machines:

25 N to 2.5 kN, $U(k = 2) = 0.001 \%$

0.5 kN to 20 kN, $U(k = 2) = 0.001 \%$

2.5 kN to 120 kN, $U(k = 2) = 0.001 \%$

10 kN to 1.2 MN, $U(k = 2) = 0.001 \%$

Hydraulic machines:

150 kN to 5 MN (hydraulic amplification), $U(k = 2) = 0.05 \%$

1.45 MN to 12 MN (strain gauged columns), $U(k = 2) = 0.05 \%$

900 kN to 30 MN (strain gauged columns), $U(k = 2) = 0.20 \%$

Other UKAS-accredited labs for ISO 376 / ASTM E74 calibrations:

Avery Weigh-Tronix

Machine 1: 20 kN to 500 kN, $U(k = 2) = 0.0050 \%$

5.5 kN to 20 kN, $U(k = 2) = 0.0081 \%$

Machine 2: 5 kN to 11 kN, $U(k = 2) = 0.0054 \%$

0.04 kN to 5 kN, $U(k = 2) = 0.0092 \%$

Machine 3: 2.2 N to 356 N, $U(k = 2) = 0.0050 \%$

Element Materials Technology Sheffield – Magna Way

Machine 1: 50 kN to 500 kN, $U(k = 2) = 0.05 \%$

Machine 2: 10 kN to 100 kN, $U(k = 2) = 0.02 \%$

Machine 3: 5 kN to 56 kN, $U(k = 2) = 0.02 \%$

Machine 4: 1 kN to 25 kN, $U(k=2) = 0.02\%$
0.5 kN to 1 kN, $U(k=2) = 0.05\%$
Machine 5: 0.1 N to 2.5 kN, $U(k=2) = 0.01\%$

Other UKAS-accredited labs for calibration of load cells (excluding proving devices) or push-pull force measuring devices:

Airbus Operations Ltd
0.25 kN to 1.2 MN, $U(k=2) = 0.36\%$

Central Calibration Services
0.2 kN to 3 MN, $U(k=2) = 0.48\%$
0.2 kN to 500 kN, $U(k=2) = 0.36\%$
0.2 N to 260 N, $U(k=2) = 0.10\%$

Defence Electronics & Components Agency
5 N to 500 N, $U(k=2) = 0.33\%$

G.T. Certification Ltd
1 N to 2.7 kN, $U(k=2) = 0.12\%$

Jaguar Land Rover Ltd
2 kN to 100 kN, $U(k=2) = 0.50\%$

Metrology and Quality Services Ltd
1 N to 500 N, $U(k=2) = 0.12\%$

Procter and Chester (Measurements) Ltd
Machine 1: 100 kN to 5 MN, $U(k=2) = 0.85\%$
Machine 2: 20 kN to 500 kN, $U(k=2) = 0.35\%$
Machine 3: 10 kN to 100 kN, $U(k=2) = 0.40\%$
0.2 kN to 10 kN, $U(k=2) = 0.30\%$

SERCAL Materials Testing Services Ltd
0.5 kN to 500 kN, $U(k=2) = 0.41\%$
0.1 N to 10 kN, $U(k=2) = 0.10\%$

Testing Calibration Services Ltd
0.05 kN to 180 kN, $U(k=2) = 0.41\%$
0.001 N to 2 kN, $U(k=2) = 0.10\%$

Trescal Ltd
0.2 kN to 100 kN, $U(k=2) = 0.40\%$
0.1 N to 2.5 kN, $U(k=2) = 0.10\%$

Numbers of UKAS-accredited laboratories for calibration of testing machines:

Compression testing machines: 13
Creep testing machines: 5
Impact testing machines: 4
Soil testing machines: 3

Tensile testing machines: 12

2,5 kN Deadweight

- **APPLIED FORCES**
 25 N to 50 N in steps of 25 N
 50 N to 500 N in steps of 50 N
 500 N to 2.5 kN in steps of 100 N
- **UNCERTAINTY OF APPLIED FORCE**
 ±0.001% over full working range
- **MODE OF OPERATION**
 Compression and tension
 Incremental and decremental loading
- **CALIBRATION METHODS**
 BS EN ISO 376
 BS 8422
 ASTM E 74
 Other relevant procedures

20 kN Deadweight

- **APPLIED FORCES**
 0.5 kN to 5 kN in steps of 0.5 kN
 5 kN to 20 kN in steps of 1 kN.
- **UNCERTAINTY OF APPLIED FORCE**
 ±0.001% over full working range
- **MODE OF OPERATION**
 Compression and tension
 Incremental and decremental loading
- **TYPES OF CALIBRATION**
 BS EN ISO 376
 BS 8422
 ASTM E 74
 Other relevant procedures

50 kN DeadWeight

The 50 kN dead weight force Machine consists of a set of weights, a loading Hanger, a platen base and a rigid main frame Supporting these components as shown

1 MN Force Standard Machine

The 1 MN force standard machine comprises of a robust four column frame with movable crosshead, a four column load suspension gear, a lever including strain controlled bearing, a tare mechanism, etc. and an electronic control system with a PC for operating the machine through a software.

120 kN Deadweight

- **APPLIED FORCES**
2.5 kN to 30 kN in steps of 2.5 kN
30 kN to 60 kN in steps of 5 kN
60 kN to 120 kN in steps of 10 kN
- **UNCERTAINTY OF APPLIED FORCE**
±0.001% over full working range
- **MODE OF OPERATION**
Compression and tension
Incremental and decremental loading
- **CALIBRATION METHODS**
BS EN ISO 376
BS 8422
ASTM E 74
Other relevant procedures

1,2 MN Deadweight

- **APPLIED FORCES**
10 kN to 1.2 MN in steps of 10 kN
- **UNCERTAINTY OF APPLIED FORCE**
±0.001% over full working range
- **MODE OF OPERATION**
Compression and tension
Incremental and decremental loading
- **TYPES OF CALIBRATION**
BS EN ISO 376
BS 8422
ASTM E 74

5 MN Hydraulic

- **APPLIED FORCES**
100 kN to 5 MN in steps of 1 kN
- **UNCERTAINTY OF APPLIED FORCE**
± 0.05% over full working range
- **MODE OF OPERATION**
Compression and tension
Incremental and decremental loading
- **TYPES OF CALIBRATION**
BS EN ISO 376
ASTM E 74
BS 8422
Other relevant procedures

12 MN Hydraulic

- **APPLIED FORCES**
400 kN to 10.8 MN
- **UNCERTAINTY OF APPLIED FORCE**
± 0.1% from 400 kN to 10.8 MN
- **MODE OF OPERATION**
Compression only
- **TYPES OF CALIBRATION**
BS 8422
ASTM E 74
Other relevant procedures

30 MN Hydraulic

- **APPLIED FORCES**
600 kN to 30 MN
- **UNCERTAINTY OF APPLIED FORCE**
over full working range
- **MODE OF OPERATION**
Compression only
- **TYPES OF CALIBRATION**
BS 8422
ASTM E 74
Other relevant procedures

Deadweight:

20 N, 200 N, 2 kN, 20 kN, 100 kN, 200 kN (temperature chamber -20 °C / +50 °C), 1 MN, and 2 MN

Hydraulic amplification:

5 MN and 16.5 MN

Dynamic: (Resulting thresholds strongly depends from the specific application. These are just “a rule of thumb” numbers)

- Shaker: - 10kN | 10 Hz till 1000 Hz (Non-Framed)
 - 400 N | 10 Hz till 5000 Hz (Non-Framed)
 - 800 N | 5 Hz till 1000 Hz (Framed)
- Hydraulic: - 20kN | 0 Hz till 200 Hz (Framed)
 - 100kN | 0 Hz till 100 Hz (Framed)

Online inquiry of dynamic testing machines

- Due to the high amount of testing machines and the focus of the project we will just evaluate the Electro- Mechanical and Servo- Hydraulic Testing machines.

Hydraulic Test Systems					
Company	Product	minimal frequency [Hz]	maximun frequency [Hz]	minimal Force [kN]	maximal Force [kN]
Shimadzu	EHF-E-Serie	unknown	50	unknown	200
Shimadzu	EHF-U-Serie	unknown	50	unknown	200
Shimadzu	EHF-L-Serie	unknown	50	unknown	20
Zwick Roell	HA-Serie	unknown	unknown	0.05	50
Zwick Roell	HB-Serie	unknown	unknown	0.05	2500
Zwick Roell	HC-Serie	unknown	unknown	0.01	25
Walter+Bai	LFV-L	unknown	unknown	unknown	50
Walter+Bai	LFV	unknown	unknown	unknown	3000
Walter+Bai	LFV - Compact	unknown	unknown	unknown	50
Instron	8872	unknown	unknown	unknown	25
Instron	8801	unknown	unknown	unknown	100
Instron	8804	unknown	unknown	unknown	500
Instron	8803	unknown	unknown	unknown	500
Instron	8805	unknown	unknown	unknown	1000
Instron	8806/8808	unknown	unknown	unknown	5000

Resonance Test Systems					
Company	Product	minimal frequency [Hz]	maximun frequency [Hz]	minimal Force [kN]	maximal Force [kN]
Shimadzu	EMT-Serie	unknown	200	unknown	1
Shimadzu	MMT-Serie	unknown	100	unknown	0.5
Zwick Roell	Vibrophore	30	300	25	1000
Sincotec	Power Swing	unknown	300	5	2000
Rumul	Mikrofon	40	250	5	20
Rumul	Testronic	40	270	50	250
Rumul	Gigaforte	unknown	1000	unknown	25
Rumul	Vibroforte	unknown	unknown	unknown	700

Linear Drive Systems					
Company	Product	minimal frequency [Hz]	maximun frequency [Hz]	minimal Force [kN]	maximal Force [kN]
Zwick Roell	LTM	unknown	120	1	10
Walter+Bai	LFV-E	unknown	unknown	unknown	12
Instron	ElectroPuls	unknown	100	unknown	10
Sincotec	Power Drive	unknown	30	1	5
Sincotec	Power Drive Direct	unknown	50	1	5

Servo-hydraulic Force Generation Machines

100-kN-Machine

- Force range: max. 100 kN**
- Signal form: arbitrary**
- Frequency range: 0 to 100 Hz**
- Accuracy: < 0.1 %**
- Status: in use**

Servo-hydraulic Force Generation Machines

20-kN-Machine

Force range: max. 20 kN

Signal form: arbitrary

Frequency range: 0 to 200 Hz

Accuracy: < 0.1 %

Status: test

2

400 N Measuring Machine for Dynamic Force Calibration

Force range	10 N to 400 N
Frequency range	10 Hz to 2000 Hz
Frequency range:	
40 Hz –	
700 Hz	0.5 %
700 Hz- 1 kHz	1.0 %
1 kHz – 2 kHz	2.0 %
rel. exp. (k=2) uncertainty	

3

10 kN Measuring Machine for Dynamic Force Calibration

Force range	Frequency range:	10 N to 1 kN
	10 Hz – 50 Hz	10 N to 2 kN
Frequency range	> 50 Hz- 2 kHz	
	10 Hz bis 2000 Hz	
rel. exp. (k=2) uncertainty	Frequency range:	
	40 Hz – 700 Hz	0.5 %
	700 Hz- 1 kHz	1.0 %
	1 kHz – 2 kHz	2.0 %

Bezeichnung: POWER SWING MOT 20 kN
 Type: Universalresonanzpulsator
 Strain gauge amplifier: carrier frequency
 Frequency range: 10...100 Hz
 Force: max. 20 kN
 Amplitude: max. 12 mm

- Resolution: 12 Bit
- Digitalisation-delay: 8 μs
- Max. sampling frequency : 110 kS/s

The test bench is an unbalanced two-mass oscillator in a vertical design. The excitation takes place via two counter-rotating unbalanced shafts, which are driven by a frequency-controlled three-phase motor.

The oscillating head, which is excited by the imbalance, is supported on the machine frame by preloaded helical compression springs and is guided centrally.

The static preload drive is located in the lower constructional part of the machine and brings the static preload by means of a spindle drive. Between the upper crosshead with the oscillating force and the machine table, the component to be tested is clamped. Together with the pretension springs, the component acts as a spring.

- parallel reading of the transducers signal not possible
- everything else works analogue
- best point to get signal of transducer at the output of the MBP 8201 Amplifier
- The dynamic transfer behavior of the MBP 8201 must be determined
- The used force transducer is an Interface-transducer, selected by the machine manufacturer SimcoTec. It would be a good idea to calibrate and investigate it separately.

Type: Servo-hydraulic
 Frequency range: up to 2 MN Hz
 Force range: max. 1 MN
 Amplitude: max. 12 mm
 Standard ISO 376 mounting parts

- The internal channels A and B, ie force and displacement, can be assigned (programmed) to the X and Y sockets.
- The measured data are not fed into the program via the GPIB bus, but fed into the program via the front X and Y sockets via a PCI-A / D converter.
- The rear X and Y jacks are free and allow one access.
- This allows a parallel tap during ongoing control.
- However, the Instron amplifier must also be investigated here.
- Whether X and Y are purely analogue or D / A-converted is currently unclear.

The vibration exciter consists of an elasticity integrated in the dynamic power flow, stimulated with an electromagnet. The magnet itself has a relatively small but constant air gap which is completely independent of the static center load.

- 1 main mass m_1 , changeable in 8 steps
- 2 counterweight m_0 formed as a worktable
- 3 specimens c
- 4 RUMUL load cell
- 5 RUMUL MAGNODYN vibration exciter system
- 6 preload springs for the static load
- 7 tensile and pressure columns for static forces
- 8 ball guides
- 9 removeable lower crosshead
- 10 ball screw
- 11 spindle drive with servomotor
- 12 vibration-damping machine supports

Adobe Acrobat Document
Extensometer

The load cells can both be mounted on the machine head and on the lower mounting table. It includes an integrated accelerometer for the compensation of the forces generated by mass forces of the oscillating devices.

Static drive

The static load is provided by a ball screw (10) with pre-strained double nut generated using a low backlash gear a servomotor is driven.

Dynamic drive

This consists essentially of the main mass 1, the counterweight 2 and the elasticity 3 of the test-sample including the other elasticities located in the dynamic power flow. These components together make up a swinging system which is set to its eigenfrequency by a feedback regulation in a controlled oscillation.

- 2-calculator principle
- Data acquisition and real-time data processing with multi-channel technology (8 digital inputs and outputs, 4 analog inputs and 2 analog outputs)
- Frequency measurement (0.001 Hz) and crack detection (0.01 Hz)
- Operation with the new RUMUL software under LabVIEW
- Multichannel online oscilloscope for simultaneous display and recording of test parameters
- These outputs F-Out; S-Out and E-Out go completely over the D / A converter.
- The scaling and source can be freely selected in the software (maximum +/- 10V).
- A direct measuring signal without A / D -> D / A conversion can not be brought out.
- All inputs go through the same A / D converter, so this must be "multiplexed". Thus, the statement of the manufacturer that all channels are in phase, not vote!
- IN-1 is another configurable measuring input. Two more can be tapped on the board.

Nennlast	kN	50	100	150
Max. statische Last	kN	50	100	150
Max. dynamische Amplitude	kN	±25	±50	±75
Max. dynamischer Schwingweg	mm	4	6	5
Frequenzbereich ¹	Hz			ca. 40–260
Frequenzstufen				8
Freier Säulenabstand ²	mm			500
Mess- und Regelgenauigkeit statisch	%			< 0,5
Mess- und Regelgenauigkeit dynamisch	%			< 0,5
Vertikaler Prüfraum ²	mm		26–612	
Max. Gesamthöhe	mm		2.688	

1 Die Prüffrequenz ist abhängig von der Steifigkeit des Prüflings inkl. Einspannvorrichtung und von den aktivierten Massen
2 Erhöhung optional möglich

- F_{max} -Sinus: 17.8 kN
- a_{max} : 1225 m/s²
- v_{max} : 2 m/s
- s_{max} : 25.4 mm (Peak Value)
- Upper resonance: 2.4 kHz

- 1 Shaker
- 2 Transducer and load mass
- 3 Air Bearing
- 4 Laser-Vibrometer
- 5 Mirror
- 6 Active oscillation damper

- F_{max} -Sinus: 400 N
- a_{max} : 60 m/s²
- m_{max} : 7 kg
- 1 Shaker
- 2 Laser-Vibrometer
- 3 Homodyn-Interferometer

- F_{max} -Sinus: 800 N
- a_{max} : 855 m/s²
- v_{max} : 1.8 m/s
- s_{max} : 10 mm (Peak Value)
- Upper resonance: >5 kHz

- 1: LVDT (Displacement)
- 2: Piston
- 3: Valve
- 4: Reference Transducer
- 5: DUT Transducer

- Supplied by one hydraulic pump
- Adjustable Frame
- Closed-Loop Control and DAQ by a Walter+Bai PCS 8000 controller

Time Series Data acquisition by the Walter+Bai Software Dion7

Calculating the transfer functions by DYI software

Simplified Model

Bare table specifications for harmonic excitation:

- $F_{max} = 17.8 \text{ kN}$
- $a_{max} = 1225 \text{ m/s}^2$
- $v_{max} = 2 \text{ m/s}$
- natural resonance frequency = 2.4 kHz (Coil Resonance)
- $m_{max} = 72.58 \text{ kg}$ (for a centered point mass)

The maximum load depends from the positing of the load

m_max [kg]	x_cow [mm]	x_ooow [mm]	a[m/s ²]
27,7777778	100	0	1196,82
15,8450704	100	1	1196,82
11,0837438	100	2	1196,82
8,52272727	100	3	1196,82
6,92307692	100	4	1196,82
5,82901554	100	5	1196,82
5,03355705	100	6	1196,82
4,42913386	100	7	1196,82
3,9543058	100	8	1196,82
3,57142857	100	9	1196,82
3,25615051	100	10	1196,82

The maximum available displacement depends from the load, operation mode and leveling

The shown simplified model will not consider any kind of overshoots. It's a „back of an envelope model“.

The different operations modes has different maximum displacements depending from the frequency.

$$x_d(f) = \text{constant} = \hat{x}$$

$$x_v(f) = \frac{v}{2 \cdot \pi \cdot f} \sim \frac{1}{f}$$

$$x_a(f) = \frac{\hat{a}}{(2 \cdot \pi)^2} \sim \frac{1}{f^2}$$

The available displacement range will be reduced by the load if the leveling is not adjusted.

$$\hat{x}_{\text{ohne-Leveling}} = \hat{x}_{PK} \cdot V_d \cdot SF = \hat{x}_{PK} \cdot \frac{(m^2 - m_L)}{m}$$

The operational upper frequency range is limited by the phase shift of the coil. This is load independent and happens slightly above the coil resonance at 2600 Hz.

At or beyond the high frequency limit of operation, the (undesired) Coil Mode is encountered. Here, the coil moves out-of-phase with the table as the elastic table/armature structure is deformed. Excessive excitation of this mode can damage the vibrator.

Although the lower frequency range is theoretically limited by the mechanical resonance we still have to consider the cross sectional stiffness.

$$\left| \frac{U(s)}{I(s)} \right| = Z(s) = \left| R + sL + \frac{\alpha^2 \cdot s}{m \cdot s^2 + k} \right|$$

$$= \left| R + j \omega \left(L + \frac{\alpha^2}{k + m (\omega)^2} \right) \right|$$

Dynamic Force Labs in Germany

ISO 148-1:all dates

Metallic materials — Charpy pendulum impact test — Part 1: Test method

103

ISO 1099:2017

Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Axial force-controlled method

41 (BAM - Discussion about the needs of dynamic calibrations at BAM (Annex1))

ISO 1352:2011

Metallic materials — Torque-controlled fatigue testing

3

ISO 12106:2017

Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Axial-strain-controlled method

3 (IMA and MPA Darmstadt - Discussion about the needs of dynamic calibrations (Annex 2 and 3))

ISO 12107:2012

Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Statistical planning and analysis of data

1 (MPA Darmstadt, see Annex 3)

ISO/DIS 12107

Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Statistical planning and analysis of data

1 (MPA Darmstadt, see Annex 3)

ISO 12108:2018

Metallic materials — Fatigue testing

4 (MPA Darmstadt: see Annex 3; BAM: see Annex 1)

ISO 12135:2002

Metallic materials — Unified method of test for the determination of quasistatic fracture toughness

4 (MPA Darmstadt: see Annex 3, MPA Stuttgart: see Annex 4)

ISO 12737:1996

Metallic materials — Determination of plane-strain fracture toughness

4 (MPA Stuttgart, see Annex 4)

ISO 14556

Steel — Charpy V-notch pendulum impact test — Instrumented test method

5 (MPA Darmstadt, see Annex 3)

ISO 15653

Metallic materials — Method of test for the determination of quasistatic fracture toughness of welds

6 (IMA, see Annex 2)

ISO 23788:2012

Metallic materials — Verification of the alignment of fatigue testing machines

1 (Trescal, see Annex 5) (Trescal with the head of the lab, Mr. Gönboldt, is one of the stakeholders)

PTB Force Lab

Prototype 20 mN facility Lutz Doerig
Uwe Brand

Intention: simultaneous measurement of force, displacement and stiffness

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> picomotors Pifoc®, 100 µm capacitive controlled mount with artifact probing pin balance: Sartorius SC2 double-walled housing 	<p>properties of balance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> resolution: 1 nN repeatability: 2.5 nN non-linearity: 9 nN <p>expected uncertainty reachable:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 20 nN in µN range temperature drift << 1 mK/min
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MEKO 2006 TC3, Round Table Jens Blummann Future Force Standard Machines at PTB 7

Research project: 10N / 2N prototype FSM

planned 2007: complete adjustable face up setup

MEKO 2006 TC3, Round Table Jens Blummann Future Force Standard Machines at PTB 4

200 N Force Standard Machine

Short name	200-N-K-NME						
Principle	deadweight						
Rel. exp. (k=2) uncertainty	2·10 ⁻⁵						
Force steps	<table border="0" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td>0.5 N, 1 N, ..., 5 N</td> <td>1 N, 2 N, ..., 10 N</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2 N, 4 N, ..., 20 N</td> <td>5 N, 10 N, ..., 50 N</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5 N, 10 N, ..., 100 N</td> <td>10 N, 20 N, ..., 200 N</td> </tr> </table>	0.5 N, 1 N, ..., 5 N	1 N, 2 N, ..., 10 N	2 N, 4 N, ..., 20 N	5 N, 10 N, ..., 50 N	5 N, 10 N, ..., 100 N	10 N, 20 N, ..., 200 N
0.5 N, 1 N, ..., 5 N	1 N, 2 N, ..., 10 N						
2 N, 4 N, ..., 20 N	5 N, 10 N, ..., 50 N						
5 N, 10 N, ..., 100 N	10 N, 20 N, ..., 200 N						

2 kN Force Standard Machine

Short name	2-KN-K-NME				
Principle	deadweight				
Rel. exp. (k=2) uncertainty	2·10 ⁻⁵				
Force steps	<table border="0" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td>50 N, 100 N, 150 N, 200 N, 250 N</td> </tr> <tr> <td>300 N, 350 N, 400 N, 500 N,</td> </tr> <tr> <td>500 N, 600 N, ..., 1000 N,</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1200 N, 1400 N, ..., 2000 N</td> </tr> </table>	50 N, 100 N, 150 N, 200 N, 250 N	300 N, 350 N, 400 N, 500 N,	500 N, 600 N, ..., 1000 N,	1200 N, 1400 N, ..., 2000 N
50 N, 100 N, 150 N, 200 N, 250 N					
300 N, 350 N, 400 N, 500 N,					
500 N, 600 N, ..., 1000 N,					
1200 N, 1400 N, ..., 2000 N					

20 kN Force Standard Machines

Short name	20-kN-K-NME
Principle	deadweight
Rel. exp. ($k=2$) uncertainty	$2 \cdot 10^{-5}$
Force steps	0.25 kN, 0.5 kN, ..., 2 kN, 2.5 kN, ..., 5 kN, 6 kN, ..., 10 kN, 12 kN, ..., 20 kN

100 kN Force Standard Machine

Short name	100-kN-K-NME
Principle	deadweight
Rel. exp. ($k=2$) uncertainty	$2 \cdot 10^{-5}$
Force steps	2 kN, 4 kN, 5 kN, 6 kN, 8 kN, 10 kN, 12 kN, 14 kN, 15 kN, 16 kN, 18 kN, 20 kN, 25 kN, ..., 50 kN, 60 kN, ..., 100 kN

Schematic diagram of the PTB's 100 kN force standard machine

Schematic diagram of the PTB's 100 kN deadweight machine

1 MN Force Standard Machine

Short name	1-MN-K-NME
Principle	deadweight
Rel. exp. ($k=2$) uncertainty	$2 \cdot 10^{-5}$
Force steps	20 kN, 40 kN, 50 kN, ..., 1000 kN

Schematic diagram of the PTB's 1 MN force standard machine

Fig. 4: Schematic diagram of the PTB's 1 MN deadweight machine

2 MN Force Standard Machine

Short name	2-MN-K-NME
Principle	deadweight
Rel. exp. ($k=2$) uncertainty	$2 \cdot 10^{-5}$
Force steps	50 kN, 60 kN, 70 kN, ..., 2000 kN

5 MN Force Standard Machine

Short name	5-MN-K-NME
Principle	hydraulic amplification
Rel. exp. ($k=2$) uncertainty	$1 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Force steps	50 kN, 100 kN, 150 kN, ..., 5000 kN

16,5 MN Force Standard Machine

Short name	16,5-MN-K-NME
Principle	hydraulic amplification
Rel. exp. ($k=2$) uncertainty	$1 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Force steps	0,1 MN, 0,2 MN, ..., 16,5 MN

Fig. 5: 15 MN hydraulic force standard machine of the PTB

VTT MIKES / FINLAND

Name:	Jani Korhonen								
email address:	jani.korhonen@vtt.fi								
NMI / Country:	VTT MIKES/FINLAND								
Services performed by NMI:	Calibration of force transducers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>							
	Calibration of testing machines	<input type="checkbox"/>							
	Mechanical tests	<input type="checkbox"/>							
	Other:	<input type="checkbox"/>							
Force machines at NMI:		< 50 N	10 N - 1000 N	10 N - 10 kN	2 kN - 100 kN	20 kN - 1000 kN			
	Deadweight	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	Amplification	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			
	Comparison	<input type="checkbox"/>							
	Other:	<input type="checkbox"/>							
NMI has CMCs in BIPM KCDB:	YES	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>							
	NO, but intend to submit in next 3 years	<input type="checkbox"/>							
	NO	<input type="checkbox"/>							
Documentary standards used for calibration of force transducers and testing machines:	SFS-EN ISO 376, SFS-EN 7500-1, SFS-EN ISO 6508-2, SFS-EN 6506-2, SFS-EN 6507-2								

<p>See diagram to right - please give details of any calibration/measurement services performed with continuous or dynamic (sinusoidal, shock, or step) forces:</p>	<p>Static calibration is performed only.</p>					
<p>Please include details of measurement principle, force range and rate/frequency, calibration method, and industrial sector:</p>	<p>Static calibration is performed only, force range is 10 N - 1000 kN for force transducers calibration.</p>					
<p>If not, please give details of any ongoing research towards providing, or industrial demands for, such services:</p>						
<p>Number of accredited force calibration laboratories in your country:</p>	<p>2 laboratories</p>					
<p>Number of accredited force testing laboratories in your country:</p>	<p>27 laboratories</p>					
<p>Most common materials tests, e.g. tensile / fatigue / hardness / impact / other:</p>	<p>Most common material tests: Tension, compression, hardness</p>					

Review of force calibration infrastructure and available facilities in Finland

- National metrology institute is VTT MIKES.
- MIKES is part of VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd.
- National standards laboratory for force is located at Kajaani.
- Total of accredited calibration laboratories in Finland 27 pcs.
- Accredited force calibration laboratories 2 pcs.

VTT MIKES national standard laboratory for force

- 5 Force Standard Machines.
 - 4 Deadweight FSMs (50 N, 1 kN, 10 kN & 100 kN)
 - 1 Hydraulic Amplification FSM (1000 kN)
- Calibration force 2 N ... 1000 kN.
- The smallest uncertainty of applied force is 0,002 % ($k=2$).
- Static force calibrations only.
- Ambient temperature during the calibrations 20 °C ± 1°C.
- Calibrated measurement devices are usually force transducers, force measurement devices, balances (e.g. hook, wheel weight and airplane) and pull force testers.
- Calibration methods in use are SFS-EN ISO 376, SFS-EN ISO 7500-1 and VTT's internal procedure KFO2.

VTT MIKES national standard laboratory for force

Measurement ranges and BIPM KCDB CMC values for force are:

Calibration or Measurement Service			Measurand level or Range			Relative Expanded Uncertainty % $k=2$
Quantity	Instrument or Artifact	Instrument Type or Method	Minimum value	Maximum value	Units	Value
Force: tension and compression	Force measuring device	Deadweight	10	10000	N	0,002
Force: tension and compression	Force measuring device	Deadweight	2	100	kN	0,005
Force: tension and compression	Force measuring device	Hydraulic amplification	20	1000	kN	0,01

VTT MIKES national standard laboratory for force

Transfer standards:

- Nominal force capacities 100 N ... 1000 kN
- Mostly compression only
 - HBM TOP Z30A force transducer, nominal value 100 N
 - Raute Precision BA3 force transducers, nominal values from 200 N to 2000 N
 - GTM KTN-D, KTN-ZD force transducers, nominal values from 5 kN to 1000 kN

Other equipment:

- HBM MGCplus, QuantumX MX238B, DMP40 and DMP41 measurement amplifiers
- HBM BN100 -bridge calibration unit

Accredited force calibration laboratories in Finland

Laboratory	Accreditation code
Inspecta Tarkastus Oy, Measuring Instruments	K004
Eurofins Expert Services Ltd.	K024

- Most of the accredited activities done by the accredited force calibration laboratories are related to on site calibration of material testing machines using static calibration method.
- Methods in use for material testing machines are SFS-EN ISO 7500-1, SFS-EN ISO 12390-4.
- Also calibration of hardness testing machines, Rockwell, Brinell, Vickers.
- Methods in use for hardness testing machines are SFS-EN ISO 6508-2, SFS-EN 6506-2, SFS-EN 6507-2.

Details of accredited force calibration activities are listed in excel-file:

18SIB08_A121-Accredited Force Calibration Laboratories_VTT.version1.20200717.xlsx

Laboratory	Object of calibration	Measurement Range	CMC, Expanded Uncertainty ($k=2$)
Inspecta Tarkastus Oy, Measuring Instruments	Force indication and force transfer of concrete testing machines SFS-EN 12390-4:2019	Compression: 100 kN $\leq F \leq 3000$ kN	$0,3 \% \cdot F$
Inspecta Tarkastus Oy, Measuring Instruments	Force/universal testing machines SFS-EN ISO 7500-1:2018	Compression $1\text{ N} \leq F \leq 3000$ kN, Tension $1\text{ N} \leq F \leq 500$	$0,25 \% \cdot F$
Eurofins Expert Services Ltd.	Force/universal testing machines SFS-EN ISO 7500-1	Compression 0,1 N – 5 MN, Tension 0,1 N – 3000 kN	Compression: $F < 1000$ kN $\pm 0,15 \% \times F$, $F > 1000$ kN $\pm 0,30 \% \times F$, tension $\pm 0,15 \% \times F$
Eurofins Expert Services Ltd.	Force/compressive testing machines, force transfer, SFS-EN 12390-4	Compression 0,2 kN – 5 MN	$0,3 \% F$
Eurofins Expert Services Ltd.	Charpy pendulum impact testing machine	SFS-EN ISO 148-2, only 2 mm head 20-250 J	$\pm 0,5$ J

Eurofins Expert Services Ltd.	Verification of hardness testing machines, Rockwell hardness testing machine SFS-EN ISO 6508-2	HRA 60-, HRB 10-, HRC 10-, HR15N 40-, HR15T 20-, HR30N 40-, HR30T 20-, HR45N 19-, HR45T 10-	0,10-0,12 HRA, 0,15-0,27 HRB, 0,13-0,14 HRC, 0,11-0,15 HR15N, 0,11-0,14 HR15T, 0,12-0,17 HR30N, 0,14-0,25 HR30T, 0,11-0,15 HR45N, 0,14-0,21 HR45T
Eurofins Expert Services Ltd.	Verification of hardness testing machines, Brinell hardness testing machine, SFS-EN 6506-2		
Eurofins Expert Services Ltd.	Verification of hardness testing machines, Vickers hardness testing machine, SFS-EN 6507-2		

CEM / SPAIN

Name:	Nieves Medina Martin								
email address:	mnmedina@cem.es								
NMI / Country:	CEM/SPAIN								
Services performed by NMI:	Calibration of force transducers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>							
	Calibration of testing machines	<input type="checkbox"/>							
	Mechanical tests	<input type="checkbox"/>							
	Other:	<input type="checkbox"/>							
Force machines at NMI:		10 N - 1000 N	200 N - 20 kN	5 kN - 500 kN	100 kN - 1500 kN				
	Deadweight	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	Amplification	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	Comparison	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	Other: Build Up	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>				
NMI has CMCs in BIPM KCDB:	YES	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>							
	NO, but intend to submit in next 3 years	<input type="checkbox"/>							
	NO	<input type="checkbox"/>							
Documentary standards used for calibration of force transducers and testing machines:	ISO 376								

<p>See diagram to right - please give details of any calibration/measurement services performed with continuous or dynamic (sinusoidal, shock, or step) forces:</p>	<p>Static (stepped steady input) and continuous are performed</p>									
<p>Please include details of measurement principle, force range and rate/frequency, calibration method, and industrial sector:</p>	<p>Static (stepped steady input) and continuous are performed maximum force range is 1500 kN for force transducers calibration.</p>									
<p>If not, please give details of any ongoing research towards providing, or industrial demands for, such services:</p>										
<p>Number of accredited force calibration laboratories in your country:</p>	<p>1 laboratory</p>									
<p>Number of accredited force testing laboratories in your country:</p>	<p>8 laboratories</p>									
<p>Most common materials tests, e.g. tensile / fatigue / hardness / impact / other:</p>	<p>Most common material tests: Tension, compression</p>									

NMI:

Deadweight 1 kN, 20 kN, and 500 kN

Hydraulic 20 MN (continuous)

LABORATORY: INTA, San Martín de la Vega (Madrid)

FACILITIES: Comparison hydraulic machine MOREHOUSE up to 25 kN for tension and compression

($U (k = 2) = 0.08 \%$, Room temperature control= $(22 \pm 1) ^\circ\text{C}$)

LABORATORY: TRESICAL IBERICA DE CALIBRACION, Zamudio (Vizcaya)
FACILITIES: Comparison hydraulic machine HOYTOM up to 50 kN for tension and compression
($U (k = 2) = 0.18 \%$, Room temperature control= $(20 \pm 1) ^\circ\text{C}$)

LABORATORY: TRESICAL ESPAÑA DE METROLOGÍA, Zaragoza
FACILITIES: Comparison hydraulic machine MICROTTEST, type EM2/200E/FR up to 200 kN for tension and compression
($U (k = 2) =$
(500 N to 2 kN: $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \times F + 2 \times 10^{-3}$ N)
(2 kN to 10 kN: $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \times F + 9 \times 10^{-2}$ N)
Room temperature control= $(19 \pm 1) ^\circ\text{C}$)

LABORATORY: MICROTTEST, Madrid

FACILITIES: Comparison hydraulic machine MICROTTEST, type EM2/300/FR up to 200 kN for tension and compression

$(U(k=2) = 1.6 \times 10^{-3} \times F, \text{ Room temperature control} = (21 \pm 2) \text{ }^\circ\text{C})$

LABORATORY: TRESICAL ESPAÑA DE METROLOGÍA, S.L., Illescas (Toledo)

FACILITIES: Comparison hydraulic machine Instron up to 100 kN for tension and compression
 $(U(k=2) = 0.1 \%, \text{ Room temperature control} = (22 \pm 5) \text{ }^\circ\text{C})$

LABORATORY: TRADELAB, Montmeló, Barcelona

FACILITIES: Comparison hydraulic machines SHIMADZU for tension and compression
 $(U(k=2) = 0.05 \%, \text{ Room temperature control} = (23 \pm 1) \text{ }^\circ\text{C})$

LABORATORY: UTILES Y MAQUINAS INDUSTRIALES S.A., Zamudio (Vizcaya)

OMEKO s.r.l.	MUGGIO'	Universal Testing Machines	1 N - 3 MN
LBG s.r.l.	AZZANO S. PAOLO	Universal Testing Machines	1 N - 3 MN
CONTROLS S.p.A.	LISCATE	Universal Testing Machines	100 N - 5 MN
METRO COM ENGINEERING S.p.A.	GARBAGNA NOVARESE	Universal Testing Machines	10 N - 6 MN
POLITECNICO DI MILANO	MILANO	Universal Testing Machines	2 N - 5 MN
S.M.I. Misure Ingegneristiche s.r.l. unipersonale	MILANO	Universal Testing Machines	10 N - 5 MN
MTS SYSTEMS s.r.l. a socio unico	TORINO	Universal Testing Machines	0.5 N - 1 MN
POLITECNICO DI TORINO Centro per la Qualità	TORINO	Universal Testing Machines	300 N - 5 MN
AQM s.r.l.	PROVAGLIO D'ISEO	Universal Testing Machines	10 N - 5 MN
UNIVERSITÀ POLITECNICA DELLE MARCHE	ANCONA	Universal Testing Machines	200 N - 5 MN
LABORATORI DI PROVE E SPERIMENTAZIONI di RFI S.p.A. - Gruppo Ferrovie dello Stato Italiane	ROMA	Universal Testing Machines	49 N - 5 MN
MATEST S.p.A. Unipersonale	TREVILOLO	Universal Testing Machines	200 N - 3 MN
MicroStudio s.r.l.	BESNATE	Universal Testing Machines	3 N - 25 kN
MESDAN LAB SERVICE	PUEGNAGO DEL GARDA	Universal Testing Machines	200 N - 10 kN

Italian UTM manufacturer

Firm	Machine Name	Vertical Capacity / kN	Horizontal Capacity / N	velocity range / mm/min	freq / Hz	Temp / °C
Easydur Italiana	Side Load	1,5	300	0.05-500	-	-
	Aura	100-1000	-	0.05-350	-	-
	3MZ	10-50	-	0.05-500	-	-
	DYNO	0.01-5	-	0.05-500	-	-
	FAT	25	-	up to 30000	1-2	-
	Aura Chasse	50-600	-	1000-3000	-	-
Galdabini	Quasar UTM	2-2000		0,0005		-
	EV Hydraulic Press	1200-15000		-		-
Metrocom Engineering	UTM Tensile Electro	5-600		-		-
	UTM Tensile Hydraulic	10-2000		-		-
LBG	TC1	1		0.1-500		10-35
	A004 (TC5)	5		0.1-500		10-35
	A005 (TC10)	10		0.1-500		10-35
	S150-25K	25		0.1-50		10-35
	S150-50K	50		0.1-50		10-35
	A006 (TC50)	50		0.1-500		10-35
	A009 (TC100)	100		0.1-350		10-35
	A009 (TC200)	200		0.1-270		10-35
	A009 (TC300)	300		0.1-250		10-35

A009 (TC400)	400		0.1-250		10-35
A042	1000		0.6-90		10-35
M055	0.01-200		0.1-30		10-35
M056	0.01-300		0.1-30		10-35
C104	1100		-		-
C114	1500		-		-
C125	2000		-		-
C135	3000		-		-

Name	Principle	Uncertainty	Force steps
700 kN compression and tension	deadweight	7 part in 50000	any 500N step of force, beginning from 2,5 up to 700 kN

<i>Name</i>	<i>Principle</i>	<i>Uncertainty</i>	<i>Force steps</i>
<i>7 MN compression and tension</i>	<i>hydraulic</i>	<i>7 part in 10000</i>	<i>any 5 kN step of force, beginning from 25 kN up to 7 MN</i>

NIS 50 kN Deadweight Machine

50 kN deadweight machine, with a stated uncertainty of 0.001 %

NIS 500 kN / 1 MN Machine

1MN deadweight machine, with a stated uncertainty of 0.001 %

LNE/France

Name	Principle	Uncertainty	Force steps
50 kN compression and tension	deadweights	2.70 th	Newton 0,5 kN

ZAG / SLOVENIA

1. General

A review of existing force calibration facilities including force standard machines, force calibration machines, and force transfer standards was performed for facilities available in Slovenia, particularly in relation to the measurement of continuous and dynamic forces.

Following operating parameters were reviewed:

- force range and components,
- frequency range,
- time-loading profiles and
- temperature

2. ZAG (accredited scope – SA LK-009, procedure ISO376 or DKD-R 3-3)

Several force calibration machines and facilities are available at ZAG: free weights up to 500 N, a 1 kN deadweights FCM, 20 kN deadweight FCM, and 600 kN FCM with reference transducer. Each facility is reviewed below. Facilities are evaluated according to Euramet cg-4 guide and are within the accredited scope of the laboratory.

Weights

Weight sets of cylindrical weights with hanger and loading frame are used for calibration of small forces in the range from 0,1 N to 500 N. The loading and unloading of weights is done by manually by hand, typically in sequential manner.

- Range 0,1 N to 500 N
- Type: weights - deadweight type - static, various manual weights with loading frame

- $W_{cmc}=0,02\%$,
- Loading direction: tension and compression
- Time loading profile: manual loading
- Temperature: ambient
- Frequency range: static

1 kN FCM, deadweight

The 1 kN deadweight force calibration machine is constructed as a sequential chain of cylindrical disc weights with the possibility of independently loading/unloading the transducer with any preselected load.

- Range 10N to 1000 N
- Type: deadweight type - static,
- Force steps (10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 80, 100, 150, 200, 250, 300, 400, 500, 600, 800, 1000) N
- $W_{cmc}=0,005\%$ (waiting for updated accreditation annex),
- Loading direction: tension and compression
- Time loading profile: sequential step loading <10 s, random force step loading/unloading selection time 150 s, immediate loading/unloading
- Temperature: ambient
- Frequency range: static

20 kN FCM, deadweight

The 20 kN deadweight force calibration machine is constructed as a sequential chain of cylindrical disc weights. Currently there is no possibility of independent loading/unloading of the transducer, only sequential loading and unloading.

- Range: 250 N to 20000 N
- Type: deadweight type - static,
- Force steps (0,25, 0,5, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18, 20)kN
- $W_{cmc}=0,01\%$,
- Loading direction: tension and compression
- Time loading profile: sequential step loading <10 s, random force step loading/unloading <180 s
- Temperature: ambient
- Frequency range: static

600 kN FCM, reference transducer

The 600 kN reference transducer force calibration machine is based on an electromechanical material testing machine upgraded with high precision 600 kN reference transducer with additional 100 kN reference transducer for the lower range and with high precision amplifier. The machine is evaluated as a static force calibration machine, but its operation is inherently based on continuous force control throughout the force range, so various continuous and dynamic loading profiles can be programmed (but in this case the force has no adequate metrological traceability).

- Range: 2 kN to 100 kN (100 kN reference), 10 kN to 600 kN (600 kN reference)
- Type: reference transducer type (comparator) with 100 kN and 600 kN reference transducer option, continuous loading possible (but lacking traceability)
- Force steps: continuous operation with any force step within the range

- $W_{cmc}=0,02\%$ to $0,05\%$ for static operation
- Loading direction: tension and compression
- Time loading profile: sequential step loading $<5\text{ s}$, random step loading/unloading $<5\text{ s}$, unloading $<1\text{ s}$
- Temperature: ambient
- Frequency range: $<1\text{ Hz}$

2000 kN FCM, reference transducer

Hydraulic Amsler loading system with manual control, with a reference transducer.

- Range: 2000 kN
- Type: reference transducer type (comparator), several transducers
- Force steps: continuous operation - manual
- $W_{cmc}=0,5\%$
- Loading direction: compression
- Time loading profile: manual hydraulic control
- Temperature: ambient
- Frequency range: static

Portable force transducer calibration system (portable FCM)

- Range: 0,1 N to 500 N
 - Type: weight sets - static
 - $W_{cmc}=0,2\%$
 - Loading direction: tension and compression
 - Time loading profile: manual loading
 - Temperature: ambient
 - Frequency range: static
-
- Range: 500 N to 100 kN
 - Type: reference transducer type (comparator) - static
 - $W_{cmc}=0,4\%$
 - Loading direction: tension and compression
 - Time loading profile: manual control
 - Temperature: ambient
 - Frequency range: static

Standards for calibration of testing machines (ISO 376 calibrated, strain gauge type):

- Weight sets from 0,1 N to 500 N, $W_{cmc} = 0,1\%$
- Force transducers for forces from 1 N to 1 MN, $W_{cmc} = 0,12\%$, tensile and compressive (class 05 or better according to ISO 376)
- Force transducers for forces from 200 kN to 5 MN, $W_{cmc} = 0,24\%$, compressive (class 1 or better according to ISO 376)

3. Other calibration facilities (review based on publicly available information as of February 2020)

Within Slovenia, there are four additional calibration laboratories active in the field of force calibration, which have their calibration capabilities assessed by the national accreditation

body (Slovenian Accreditation - SA). The review is based on information available from the published accreditation scope annexes of these laboratories. Most of these laboratories do not specify any link of the calibration procedures to international standards, so they are unable to provide calibration and classification according to ISO 376 standard.

3.1. ALBA d.o.o. (accredited scope – SA LK-027, procedure based on DKD-R 3-3)

Weights set:

- Range: 10 N to 1200 N
- Type: free weights - static
- $W_{cmc} = 0,1 \% \text{ to } 0,38 \%$
- Loading direction: compression
- Time loading profile: manual loading
- Temperature: ambient
- Frequency range: static

Portable force calibration system with reference transducer

- Range: 10 N to 1200 N
- Type: portable FCM with reference transducer
- $W_{cmc} = 0,34 \% \text{ to } 0,63 \%$
- Loading direction: compression
- Time loading profile: manual loading
- Temperature: ambient
- Frequency range: static

3.2. Lotrič Metrology d.o.o. (accredited scope – SA LK-008, no reference to international guidelines or standards)

Weights set:

- Range: 1 N to 5000 N
- Type: free weights
- $W_{cmc} = 0,013 \% \text{ to } 0,07 \%$
- Loading direction: not known
- Time loading profile: manual loading
- Temperature: ambient
- Frequency range: static

Standards for calibration of testing machines (ISO 376 calibrated, strain gauge type):

- Force transducers for forces from 200 N to 200 kN, $W_{cmc} = 0,25 \%$, tensile
- Force transducers for forces from 200 N to 3000 kN, $W_{cmc} = 0,25 \%$, compressive

3.3. SIJ Ravne Systems d.o.o. (accredited scope – SA LK-004, no reference to international guidelines or standards)

Weights set:

- Range: 10 N to 1000 N
- Type: free weights
- $W_{cmc} = 0,2 \%$
- Loading direction: tension and compression

- Time loading profile: manual loading
- Temperature: ambient
- Frequency range: static

Reference transducer system

- Range: 1 N to 100 kN
- Type: loading system with reference transducer(s)
- $W_{cmc}=0,25\%$
- Loading direction: tension and compression
- Time loading profile: not known
- Temperature: ambient
- Frequency range: static

Standards for calibration of testing machines (ISO 376 calibrated, strain gauge type):

- Force transducers for forces from 10 N to 500 kN, $W_{cmc} = 0,2\%$, tensile and compressive
- Force transducers for forces from 500 N to 5 MN, $W_{cmc} = 0,75\%$, compressive

3.4. **SIQ** (accredited scope – SA LK-001, no reference to international guidelines or standards)

Weights set:

- Type: free weights
- Range: 0,5 N to 400 N
- $W_{cmc}= 0,25\%$ to $2,0\%$
- Loading direction: tension and compression
- Time loading profile: manual loading
- Temperature: ambient
- Frequency range: static

Portable force calibration system with reference transducer

- Type: portable FCM with reference transducer
- Range: 10 N to 1200 N
- $W_{cmc}= 0,4\%$ to $4,0\%$
- Loading direction: tension and compression
- Time loading profile: manual loading
- Temperature: ambient
- Frequency range: static

NIMJ AIST / JAPAN

Name:	HAYASHI Toshiyuki																			
email address:	t-hayashi@aist.go.jp																			
NMI / Country:	NMIJ AIST/JAPAN																			
Services performed by NMI:	Calibration of force transducers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																		
	Calibration of testing machines	<input type="checkbox"/>																		
	Mechanical tests	<input type="checkbox"/>																		
	Other:	<input type="checkbox"/>																		
Force machines at NMI:			< 10 N	10 N - 1 kN	1 kN - 10 kN	10 kN - 100 kN	100 kN - 1 MN	> 1 MN												
	Deadweight	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>																	
	Amplification	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																
	Comparison	<input type="checkbox"/>																		
	Other:	<input type="checkbox"/>																		
NMI has CMCs in BIPM KCDB:	YES	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																		
	NO, but intend to submit in next 3 years	<input type="checkbox"/>																		
	NO	<input type="checkbox"/>																		
Documentary standards used for calibration of force transducers and testing machines:	JIS B7728:2013 identical with ISO 376																			

<p>See diagram to right - please give details of any calibration/measurement services performed with continuous or dynamic (sinusoidal, shock, or step) forces:</p>	<p>NMIJ serves calibrations only with quasi-static forces.</p>	
<p>Please include details of measurement principle, force range and rate/frequency, calibration method, and industrial sector:</p>		
<p>If not, please give details of any ongoing research towards providing, or industrial demands for, such services:</p>	<p>NMIJ has no on going research on dynamic force calibrations; however, industry needs information of frequency response of force measuring instruments: fatigue test for material developments, shock responses for safety test of vehicles, and so on.</p>	
<p>Number of accredited force calibration laboratories in your country:</p>	<p>Total 15 laboratories (12 ones using JIS B7728:2013 identical with ISO 376:2011 and 3 ones using others)</p>	
<p>Number of accredited force testing laboratories in your country:</p>	<p>32 laboratories</p>	
<p>Most common materials tests, e.g. tensile / fatigue / hardness / impact / other:</p>	<p>Tensile, fatigue, hardness and impact tests are commonly performed in Japan. Most common test may be tensile.</p>	

20 kN DWMS OF NMIJ

The 20 kN force standard machine, as shown, has a loading frame acting as a 500 N weight and two series of linkage weights.

The upper series consists of a 500 kN weight and nine 1 kN-weights, and the lower one has five 2 kN weights.

The two series of the linkage weights are placed on crossbeams of weight supporters and can be moved up and down independently by driving each of the weight supporters using motors.

Fig.1 20 kN DEAD WEIGHT MACHINE

Fig.2 20 kN DEAD WEIGHT MACHINE

Name	Principle	Uncertainty	Force steps
20 kN (2 tf)	deadweight	<1/100000 of the maximum force	Up to 20 kN (2 tf) with the step of 1 kN (0,1 tf) by the combination of weights

Name	Principle	Uncertainty	Force steps
53,9366 kN (5,5 tf)	deadweight	1/200 000 of the maximum force	From 9,8067 kN (1 tf) to 53,9366 kN (5,5 tf) with the step of 4,9033 kN (0,5 tf) by the combination of weights

100 kN DWM OF NIMT

The 100 kN force standard machine in NIMT, as shown in Fig. 1, has a loading frame acting as a 1 kN weight and a series of linkage weights consisting of thirteen 1 kN weights, four 2 kN weights, a 3 kN weight, seven 5 kN weights, and five 10 kN weights.

It can calibrate force transducers and test pieces of four rated capacities, namely, 10 kN, 20 kN, 50 kN, and 100 kN, each having ten force steps of equal increments. A 10 % overloading test can also be performed for these ranges; that is, the maximum load of this DWM is 110 kN.

When the loading frame is at rest, it is supported on a fixed slab, and its alignment is maintained by an automatic centering jig provided on the slab.

The force transducer or the test piece under calibration is set at the center of the compression table, or is hung at the center of the tensile fitting.

The compression table and the tensile fitting move as one and lift the force transducer and the loading frame together. Thus, the loading frame is separated from the centering jig, and the first load is applied to the force transducer.

After the compression table and the tensile fitting stop moving, the crossbeam, which supports the other linkage weights, moves down to apply required forces one by one.

Fig.1 100 kN LEVER TYPE FORCE STANDARD MACHINE

Name	Principle	Uncertainty	Force steps
117,68 kN (12 tf) Nominal capacity is 98,067 kN (10 tf)	lever	1/200000 of the nominal capacity	Up to 117,68 kN (12 tf) with the step of 0,981 kN (0,1 tf) by the combination of weights

Fig.1 300 kN LEVER TYPE FORCE STANDARD MACHINE

Fig.2 300kN LEVER TYPE FORCE STANDARD MACHINE

Name	Principle	Uncertainty	Force steps
360 kN (36 tf)	lever	1/50 000 of the nominal capacity	Up to 360 kN (36 tf) with the step of 7 kN (0,7 tf) by the combination of weights

540 kN DWMS OF NMJ

The 540 kN force standard machine of NMJ, has a loading frame acting as a 29.4 kN (3000 kgf) weight and two series of linkage weights.

The upper series consists of ten 4.9 kN (500 kgf) weights and the lower one has a 19.6 kN (2000 kgf) weight and nine 49 kN (5000 kgf) weights.

The upper and lower linkage weights are placed on crossbeams of each weight supporter.

They are connected to a hydraulic motor through a chain link and to a hydraulic jack through a pair of lifting rods. The hydraulic jack is placed at the top of the framework of the DWM, and it drives the loading frame and the lower linkage weights up and down. The hydraulic motor is installed just below the loading table.

55TON-FORCE DEAD WEIGHT MACHINE

Name	Principle	Uncertainty	Force steps
539,366 kN (55 tf)	deadweight	1/200000 of the maximum force	From 29,4200 kN (3 tf) to 539,3 kN (55 tf) with the step of 4,90; (0,5 tf) by the combination of weights

Name	Principle	Uncertainty	Force steps
776,80 kN(220 tf) Nominal capacity is 980,67 kN(100 tf)	lever	1/5000 of the nominal capacity	52 weights of cast iron. Up to 776,80kN (220 tf) with the step 0,981 kN (0,1 tf)

Fig.1 570 tf HYDRAULIC FORCE STANDARD MACHINE

Fig.2 570 tf HYDRAULIC FORCE STANDARD MACHINE

Name	Principle	Uncertainty	Force steps
5589,8 kN (570 tf)	hydraulic	1/2000 of the maximum force	From 49,03 kN (5 tf) to 5589,8 kN (570 tf) with the step of 49,03 kN (5 tf) by the combination of weights

Fig.1 20 MN HYDRAULIC FORCE STANDARD MACHINE

Fig.2 20 MN HYDRAULIC FORCE STANDARD MACHINE

Name	Principle	Uncertainty	Force steps
20 MN (2000 tf)	Hydraulic	$1/10\ 000$ of the maximum force	Up to 20 MN (2000 tf) with the step of 0,7 MN (70 tf) by the combination of weights

INMETRO / BRASIL

REPORT OF SURVEY FOR FORCE METROLOGY IN THE GROUP OF FORCE AND TORQUE OF SIM March 10th, 2020

The questionnaire intended to collect information from all NMIs and DIs of the InterAmerican Metrology System (SIM) which work in the Field of FORCE METROLOGY.

Information was collected in August and September 2019 and below is the box with the information of which SIM countries responded to the Survey (15 countries contacted and 14 answered)

PART 1 - Review of existing force calibration facilities including force standard machines, force calibration machines, and force transfer standards

1) Regardless the declared CMC/KCDB, does your NMI carry out services for:

2) Infrastructure - Machines or instrument sets that exist in your lab:

Other principles: Force Transducer, Testing machines for mechanical testings, Small force research and special tests, 2 MN load cell, ISO7500-1 up to 5MN Compression

3) Does your NMI/DI have CMCs in Force declared in the Appendix C of the KCDB/BIPM?

4) What standards/guidelines/recommendations are adopted in your NMI/DI for the Calibration/Verification of Force Measuring Instruments or Systems in your country, including testing machines?

ISO 376, ISO 7500, ASTM E74, ASTM E4

PART 2 - Information particularly in relation to the measurement of continuous and dynamic forces

5) Does your NMI carry out services for calibration/measurement in regimes with CONTINUOUS FORCE?

6) If you choose (A), (B) or (C) options in the previous question, please respond the following questions about CONTINUOUS FORCE, if possible:

PRINCIPLE USED:

Force Comparator Machine, quasi-static force, Machine Calibration for vehicle shock absorber tests, Comparison using a test machine as generator.

RANGES OF FORCE (N) AND FORCE RATE (N/s):

- From 10kN up to 1000kN. Maximum rate: 70N/s to 7kN/s
- From 10 N to 3 MN to calibrate force instruments and uniaxial testing machines
- 50 N to 1 MN with rate 0.02 N/s
- 20 N a 1000 kN
- 3000 kN. 0.00001 N/S
- Up to 5kN
- 20 kN
- 10 kN to 1 MN

INDUSTRY SECTORS:

- Construction (3x cited)
- Metal-mechanic (2x cited)
- Secondary calibration laboratories
- Auto parts (2x cited)
- Plastics
- Steelmaker
- Aeronautical
- Mining

7) Does your NMI carry out services for calibration/measurement in regimes with DYNAMIC FORCE?

8) If you choose (A), (B) or (C) options in the previous question, please respond the following questions about DYNAMIC FORCE, if possible:

PRINCIPLE USED:

- Primary system (CENAM, NIST)
- Sinusoidal force calibration (4x cited)
- Impact

RANGES OF FORCE (N), FREQUENCY (Hz) AND/OR FORCE RATE (N/s):

- up to 1 kN and up to 2000 Hz
- Ranges: 25 kN, 250 kN and 500 kN, variable force rates.
- up to 5 kN, up to 20 Hz
- 10 Hz - 2 kHz; capacity 2 kN
- 0.1 kN to 3000 kN.

METHOD (TO BE) ADOPTED:

- ASTM or AASHTO.
- ISO 4965
- NIST methodology and experiment design

INDUSTRY SECTORS:

- Aerospace
- Construction sector
- Auto parts
- Steelmaker
- Aeronautical
- Orthopedic
- Aeronautics
- Materials/fatigue
- Dissemination of SI unit

PART 3 - Information about Accreditation Body on Force Calibration and Test

9) Is there an Accreditation Body for Calibration and/or Test Labs in your country?

How many accredited Force Calibration Labs are there in your country?

How many accredited Force Test Labs are there in your country?

10) About the existing material testing machines and other test stands in your country, check the options that best describe the fields most demanded/attended in the industry

11) General comments:

- Workshops to do with SIM (characterization of force systems and standards)
- Support for the acquisition of force measurements standards
- Access first-hand technical information on force metrology
- Needs of more intercomparisons (CMCs statement)
- Research and development on Multiaxial force and build up systems

VSL / NETHERLANDS

Name	Principle	Uncertainty	Force steps
5,40 kN Tension and Compression	deadweight	0,49-0,96 kN $\times 2 \cdot 10^{-4}$ 0,98-1,96 kN $\times 7 \cdot 10^{-4}$ 1,96-5,40 kN $\times 2 \cdot 10^{-4}$	55 pairs of 5 kg each, made of stainless steel

Name	Principle	Uncertainty	Force steps
500 kN Tension and Compression	deadweight	Less than $7 \cdot 10^{-4}$	Independent of each other - except for the first two steps of 5 kN

Part of the 500 kN deadweight machine at operating level.

Schematic principle of the 500 kN deadweight machine.

Name	Principle	Uncertainty	Force steps
245 kN Tension and Compression	Lever (ratio 70:7)	$< 7 \cdot 10^{-4}$	24 pairs of 50 each + 4 single weight of 25 each made of steel and coated with paint

Name	Principle	Uncertainty	Force steps
245 kN compression 98 kN tension	deadweight plus lever (ratio 70:7)	$< 7 \cdot 10^{-4}$	24 pairs, each 2x50 kg and 4weight of 25 kg each steel coated with paint

Name	Principle	Uncertainty	Force steps
2300 N compression and tension	deadweight	up to 250 N: $< 5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ between 250 and 800 N: $< 2,5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ from 800 up to 2500 N: $< 2 \cdot 10^{-5}$	Tension: min load 20N, min load increments 10 N Compression: min load 20N, first load increment 20N and next 10N

INM /ROMANIA

Name	Principle	Uncertainty	Force steps
10 N compression and tension	deadweight	$5 \cdot 10^{-5}$	7...70

Fig. 1
MASINA ETALON CU LINGARILE DIRECTE 10 N (1 kg)
NORMALIZATA SI UNIFORMIZATA 10 N (1 kg)

Name	Principle	Uncertainty	Force steps
10 N compression and tension	deadweight	$5 \cdot 10^{-5}$	5...25-50...500-600...7000

Name	Principle	Uncertainty	Force steps
50 kN compression and tension	deadweight	$5 \cdot 10^{-3}$	50-100...-500-600...-1000-1250

Name	Principle	Uncertainty	Force steps
100 kN compression and tension	deadweight	$5 \cdot 10^{-6}$	100-200...-1000 1000...-10000

RISE/SWEDEN

Name	Principle	Uncertainty	Force steps
6 MN compression	Build-up procedure with loadcells	$5 \cdot 10^{-4}$	Any step or force from 0 - 6 MN

<p>Documentary standards used for calibration of force transducers and testing machines:</p>	<p>ISO 376</p>					
<p>See diagram to right - please give details of any calibration/measurement services performed with continuous or dynamic (sinusoidal, shock, or step) forces:</p>	<p>None at NMISA Force Lab.</p>					
<p>Please include details of measurement principle, force range and rate/frequency, calibration method, and industrial</p>	<p>None at NMISA Force Lab.</p>					
<p>If not, please give details of any ongoing research towards providing, or industrial demands for, such services:</p>	<p>NMISA Force lab has not received direct demand for such services</p>					
<p>Number of accredited force calibration laboratories in your country:</p>	<p>13</p>					
<p>Number of accredited force testing laboratories in your country:</p>	<p>20</p>					
<p>Most common materials tests, e.g. tensile / fatigue / hardness / impact / other:</p>	<p>Tensile and Impact Testing</p>					

<p>Documentary standards used for calibration of force transducers and testing machines:</p>	<p>ISO 376 for force transducers ISO 7500-1 for testing machines</p>	
<p>See diagram to right - please give details of any calibration/measurement services performed with continuous or dynamic (sinusoidal, shock, or step) forces:</p>	<p>quasi-static</p>	
<p>Please include details of measurement principle, force range and rate/frequency, calibration method, and industrial sector:</p>	<p>Direct comparison from 10 % to 100 %, 40 N to 5 MN, about 100 certificate every years, transportations and constructions</p>	
<p>If not, please give details of any ongoing research towards providing, or industrial demands for, such services:</p>		
<p>Number of accredited force calibration laboratories in your country:</p>	<p>23 laboratories for force measuring devices, 41 laboratories for testing machines.</p>	
<p>Number of accredited force testing laboratories in your country:</p>	<p>More than 41 laboratories</p>	
<p>Most common materials tests, e.g. tensile / fatigue / hardness / impact / other:</p>	<p>Tensile and compression for metal and concrete</p>	

VIM / VIETNAM

Name:	Pham Thanh Ha																			
email address:	hapt@vmi.gov.vn																			
NMI / Country:	VIM/VIETNAM																			
Services performed by NMI:	Calibration of force transducers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																		
	Calibration of testing machines	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																		
	Mechanical tests	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																		
	Other:	<input type="checkbox"/>																		
Force machines at NMI:			< 10 N	10 N - 1 kN	1 kN - 10 kN	10 kN - 100 kN	100 kN - 1 MN	> 1 MN												
	Deadweight	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>												
	Amplification	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>												
	Comparison	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>												
	Other:	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>												
NMI has CMCs in BIPM KCDB:	YES	<input type="checkbox"/>																		
	NO, but intend to submit in next 3 years	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																		
	NO	<input type="checkbox"/>																		

<p>Documentary standards used for calibration of force transducers and testing machines:</p>	<p>ISO 376:2011; ASTM E74-18; ISO 7500-1:2018; VietNam documentary standards: VMI.CP-60:2018</p>							
<p>See diagram to right - please give details of any calibration/measurement services performed with continuous or dynamic (sinusoidal, shock, or step) forces:</p>	<p>Calibration/measurement services performed with steady input and stepped steady input</p>							
<p>Please include details of measurement principle, force range and rate/frequency, calibration method, and industrial sector:</p>	<p>Measurement principle: Deadweight; Hydraulic Amplification; Lever Amplification; Multiple Transducer System. Force range: 1 kN to 5000 kN</p>							
<p>If not, please give details of any ongoing research towards providing, or industrial demands for, such services:</p>	<p>N/A</p>							
<p>Number of accredited force calibration laboratories in your country:</p>	<p>About 25 laboratories</p>							
<p>Number of accredited force testing laboratories in your country:</p>	<p>About 60 laboratories</p>							
<p>Most common materials tests, e.g. tensile / fatigue / hardness / impact / other:</p>	<p>Most common material tests: Tensile,bend,hardness; Infrequent test: Impact</p>							

NIM/CHINA

Chinese 100 tf deadweight machine

<i>Name</i>	<i>Principle</i>	<i>Uncertainty</i>	<i>Force steps</i>
100 tf compression and tension	deadweight	Better than one part in 10^5	Any 1 tf step on force beginning from 2 tf up to 101 tf (100 steps)

<i>Name</i>	<i>Principle</i>	<i>Uncertainty</i>	<i>Force steps</i>
100 kN	deadweight	$5 \cdot 10^{-4}$	100-200-...-7000- 7000-...-70000

NPLI /INDIA

Name	Principle	Uncertainty	Force steps
7 MN compression and tension	7-700 kN deadweight 700-7000 kN lever transmission	7-700 kN $\leq 2.70\%$ 700-7000 kN $\leq 2.70\%$	Any 7 kN step or force from 7 kN up to 70 kN Any 2 kN step or force from 70 kN up to 700 kN Any 70 kN step or force from 70 kN up to 7000 kN

NMI/AUSTRALIA

Name	Principle	Uncertainty	Force steps
5655 N	deadweight	1 part in 50,000	50 N thereafter any force which is a multiple of 5 N up to the maximum force 5655 N

Diagram of 7254 Deadweight Standardizing Machine Capacity = 123,000 lbf

Labels:
 COMPRESSION SPACE - 2" WIDE BY 42" HIGH
 ADJUSTABLE CROSS-HEAD
 TENSION SPACE - 2" WIDE BY 42" BETWEEN 40 PLATES
 LOAD RELIEVING & PRESSURE TRANSMITTING BEARS
 LIFTING PLATFORM SUPPORT SCREWS FOR LONG TERM TESTS
 LIFTING PLATFORM SUPPORT SCREWS
 WEIGHTS SHACKLED FROM LIFTING FRAME AND EACH OTHER
 LIFTING PLATFORM SUPPORT SCREWS
 LIFTING PLATFORM SUPPORT SCREWS
 WEIGHTS SUPPORTED ON PIN & PIN EACH OTHER BY 3 POINT SUPPORTS
 WEIGHT PIN SHACKLED TO LOWER WEIGHTS

Legend:
 ■ FIXED FRAME
 ■ LOADING FRAME (1000 lbf)
 ■ WEIGHT PIN 800 lbf, 10-2000 lbf & 3-1000 lbf WEIGHTS
 ▨ LIFTING PLATFORM FOR 800 lbf WEIGHT 800 lbf WEIGHT PIN (LOADING FRAME)
 ▨ LIFTING PLATFORM FOR 1000 lbf WEIGHTS
 ■ WEIGHT PIN 800 lbf & 10-2000 lbf WEIGHTS
 ■ LIFTING PLATFORM FOR 8000 lbf WEIGHT PIN AND 8000 lbf WEIGHTS
 ▨ LIFTING PLATFORM FOR 4000 lbf WEIGHT PIN & 4000 lbf WEIGHTS
 ■ WEIGHT PIN 4000 lbf (10-4000 lbf WEIGHTS)

AVERY

Name	Principle	Uncertainty	Force steps
723,000 lbf (550 kN)	deadweight	7 part in 50,000	7700 lbf (4,9 kN) and then in steps of 200 N up to 550 kN

NIST / USA

Capacity:			
kN	4448	1334	498
(klbf)	(1000)	(300)	(112)
Minimum Load:			
kN	222	44	13
(klbf)	(50)	(10)	(3)
Minimum Increment:			
kN	222	44	4.4
(klbf)	(50)	(10)	(1)
Time to Capacity, s	345	292	274
Compression Setup Space:			
Vertical, m	1.98	1.65	1.02
Horizontal, m	0.86	0.91	0.71
Tension Setup Space:			
Vertical, m	4.45	2.49	2.16
Horizontal, m	1.17	0.91	0.71

The two weight stacks of the NIST 112 klbf (498 kN) deadweight machine.

Schematic drawing of NIST deadweight machines 112 klbf

The NIST 300 klbf (1.33 MN) deadweight machine.

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15. www.gov.br/inmetro/pt-br
- 16.